

Modeling Process Physics of Thick Section UHMWPE Structures

John J. Tierney, Alex Vanarelli, Molla Ali, Ahmad, Jesse Brown,
Joseph M. Deitzel, John W. Gillespie Jr.,

University of Delaware Center for Composite Materials (UD-CCM)

Michael Yeager, Jeffrey Staniszewski, Travis A. Bogetti

DEVCOM Army Research Laboratory, Aberdeen Proving Ground, MD, USA

University of
Pittsburgh®

UNIVERSITY OF
DELAWARE

CENTER FOR
COMPOSITE MATERIALS

UMASS
AMHERST

Consolidation during UHMWPE Processing

- Significant porosity (>30%) exists in received 4-ply UHMWPE laminate that requires **high pressure** to consolidate panels
- The **high pressures** needed to densify parts damages filaments that reduces performance.
- **High pressure** processing also increases process complexity and capital costs
- Can we leverage a **Degassing** step to reduce the need for **High Pressure**?

* Manufacturer Recommended Process Cycle

* Source: Dyneema Customer Information Sheet

Unit Cell TPU Infusion Model

Pair of Coupled First Order ODEs

$$\dot{a} = \frac{a}{2} \left\{ - \left(\frac{1}{\eta_{eff}(v_f)} + \frac{6K(v_f)}{\eta(t) \cdot a^2} \right) \sigma_{el}(v_f) - \frac{3K(v_f)}{\eta(t) \cdot a^2} \frac{a+b}{a} p_{app}(t) \right\}$$

$$\dot{h} = \frac{h}{2} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{\eta_{eff}(v_f)} - \frac{6K(v_f)}{\eta(t) \cdot a^2} \right) \sigma_{el}(v_f) - \frac{3K(v_f)}{\eta(t) \cdot a^2} \frac{a+b}{a} p_{app}(t) \right\}$$

Initial Conditions Related to the Laminate Porosity

$$b(0) = \frac{v_{f0} \cdot d_v}{2} \quad a(0) = \frac{d_v}{2} - \frac{v_{f0} \cdot d_v}{2}$$

Fiber Volume Fraction

$$v_f = \frac{v_{f0} \cdot a_0 \cdot h_0}{a \cdot h}$$

Volume of Void Left

$$V_{void} = (a_0 + b_0 - a) \cdot h + (a_0 \cdot h_0 - a \cdot h)$$

Effective Viscosity

$$\eta_{eff}(t) = \eta(t) \frac{1}{1 - \sqrt{\frac{v_f}{v_{fmax}}}}$$

Fiber Stress

$$\sigma_{el}(v_f) = S \cdot \ln \left(\frac{v_{fmax} - v_f}{v_{fmax} - v_{fmin}} \right)$$

TPU Viscosity - Temperature

Developed Process Optimization Software

- Realtime LabVIEW GUI for optimizing UHMWPE Process cycle
- Operates in two modes:
 - Parametric : compares any two variables for time to fully consolidate laminate
 - Process Cycle : time-temperature-pressure cycle
 - Heat Transfer Mode (in development) to optimize cycle based on geometry, boundary materials etc.

VOID CONSOLIDATION MODEL Admin Data

G:_Contracts_PITT\Models\VOID_unit_cell_model\Model
Inputs\INPUT_test_run.txt Load Save

Model Inputs

	Low Value	High Value	Units	
Dimensions	-----	-----		0
Length of Region: L	0.0254	0.0254	m	1
Width of Region: w	0.0254	0.0254	m	2
Initial Ply Thickness: ti	0.0002	0.0002	m	3
Process Conditions	-----	-----	----	4
Applied Pressure P	6.89	68.9	MPa	5
Applied Force: F	0	0	N	6
	00.0000	0.0000	m/s	7
Total Time: t	200	200	min	8
Temperature: Ti	130	130	C	9
End Temperature: Te	100	300	C	10
Intimate Contact Model	-----	-----		11
Initial Roughness: Rc	0.1827	0.1827		12
Void Model	-----	-----		13
Initial Void Content: Vo	26	26	%	14
Void Spacing: vs	0.00001	0.0001	m	15
Permeability: k	.0013	.013	$\times 10^{-12}$	16
Initial Void Pressure: Vp	.101	1	Mpa	17
Initial Void Temperature:	298.1600	298.1600	K	18
Original Fiber Volume	40	60	%	19
Glass Transition Temperature: Tg	416.1600	416.1600	K	20
Resin Viscosity	1e3	1e5	Pa.	21
Void Venting	0	1	0 open- 1	22
Model Settings				23
Time Steps	1000	1000	n	24

Parametric Study **Process Cycle**

Value: 110

Time (min)	Temperature	Pressure
0	25	2
2.5	45	2
5	77	2
7.5	93	2
10	110	16.5
15	120	16.5
20	130	16.5
45	130	16.5
50	60	16.5
51	45	.101

Study to Run Process Cycle Solve

Solver Void Spacing: vs 0.00001 Permeability: k 0.013

Void Consolidation

Parametric Study

Model Inputs Process Cycle Results

Results & Key Findings

- Time to Consolidate laminate based on void spacing, 130C isothermal
- Indicator of how microstructure affects consolidation times as a function of pressure

Results & Key Findings

- Time to Consolidate laminate based on peak temperature and void spacing
- Indicator of how peak part temperature affects fill times for low- and high-pressure cases
- Process times driven by lowest peak temperature in part

- Abaqus Model of mold, bladders and part in development
- Simple stack experiments ongoing to validate thermal model

Addition of Heat Transfer Model

Effect of Variation of Thermal Conductivity

Integration of Thermal Model with Void Solution

Integrated Thermal Solution with Void Consolidation Model to predict through thickness consolidation

Solve Through Thickness

CDS 2025 Heat Transfer

Unit Cell Void Model

Void Consolidation

100 micron Void Spacing 1ATM void Pressure
Recommended Process Cycle

Over Time

Through Thickness

Void Consolidation

200 micron Void Spacing 1ATM void Pressure
Recommended Process Cycle

Over Time

Through Thickness

Void Consolidation

500 micron Void Spacing 1ATM void Pressure
Recommended Process Cycle

Over Time

Through Thickness

Thickness As a Function of Void Spacing

Interfacial Contact Development

20% Initial Contact

Recommended Process Cycle

Over Time

Through Thickness

Interfacial Contact Development

5% Initial Contact

Recommended Process Cycle

Over Time

Through Thickness

HB210- Thick Section Thermal Profile

- 0.5" Panel under vacuum
- 8 thermocouples through thickness
- Panel heated to 100C
- Powered off at 180 minutes

Effective Thermal Conductivity

Experimental Results

Time Temperature Plot A 3

Model Predictions: $K = 0.16 \text{ W/m.K}$

Model Predictions: $K = 0.10 \text{ W/m.K}$

Thermal Cycle Time Reduction

	Time (m)	Temperature
(1) Initial	0	25
(6) Ramp	1	120
(9) Step	80	120
(10) Step	350	120
(14) Step	351	25
-16) Step	450	25

	Time (m)	Temperature
(1) Initial	0	25
(6) Ramp	40	140
(9) Ramp	42	130
(10) Step	80	120
(14) Step	350	120
-16) Step	351	25
-17) Step	450	25

120 minutes to Steady State (with surface losses)

95 minutes to Steady State (with surface losses)

Thermal Cycle Time Reduction

	Time (m)	Temperature
(1) Initial	0	25
(6) Ramp	30	160
(9) Ramp	42	125
(10) Step	80	120
(14) Step	200	95
-16) Step	202	25
-17) Step	450	25

75 Minutes to Steady State (with surface losses)

	Time (m)	Temperature
(1) Initial	0	25
(6) Step	1	160
(9) Ramp	42	125
(10) Step	80	120
(14) Step	200	95
-16) Step	202	25
-17) Step	450	25

55 Minutes to Steady State (with surface losses)

Thermal Analysis: CDS2025.1

Real-Time Thermal-Process-Stress Analysis Software

The screenshot displays the CDS 2025 software interface for thermal analysis. The interface is divided into several main sections:

- Materials:** A tree view on the left lists various materials and laminates, including Fibers, Matrix, Plies, Laminas, and Laminates. The "Thermal hot plate" option is selected under the Analysis section.
- Model Input:** The central area shows a 3D model of a red rectangular plate. Below the model, the "1D Steady State Thermal Analysis of composite laminate" is configured. The "Process Conditions" table is as follows:

Process Velocity: Vp	0
Time Steps: ts	100
Initial Temperature: Ti	25
Nodes Per Ply: n	4
Number of Cycles, Passes	1
- Boundary Conditions:** A table on the right defines the upper and lower boundary conditions over time.

	Time (m)	Temperature	Boundary
(1) Initial	0	25	50.00
(6) Ramp	1.00	95.00	50.00
(9) Step	80	95.00	50.00
(10) Step	180.00	95.00	20.00
(14) Step	182.00	25	20.00
(16) Step	450	25	20.00
- Results:** The bottom section shows two plots. The left plot is a "Time Temperature" contour plot showing a color gradient from blue (low temperature) to red (high temperature) across the plate. The right plot is a "Time Temperature" graph showing the temperature profile through the thickness (Bottom, Top, Cursor) over time, with a peak temperature of approximately 95°C.

Simulation Workflow

Thermal Properties

Standard View Table View

Transport properties for HB-210

	Value	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Thermal Conductivity (x-direction): K1	0.16	0	1500
Thermal Conductivity (y-direction): K2	0.16	0	10000
Moisture Diffusion Coefficient: D1	0.2	0	1000
Moisture Diffusion Coefficient: D2	0.00E+00	0	1.00E-04
Moisture Diffusion Coefficient: D3	0.00E+00	0	1.00E-04
Electrical Conduction: R1	0.00E+00	0	1.00E-04
Electrical Conduction: R2	0	100	1
Electrical Conduction: R3	0	100	1

Thermal Conductivity (x-direction): K1 1.60E-1

Boundary Conditions

Use Laminar Use Selected from Tree

1D Steady State Thermal Analysis of composite laminate
time or length based input
Solution coupled with stress analysis

Process Conditions Domain Time Based

Process Velocity: Vp	0
Time Steps: ts	100
Initial Temperature: Ti	25
Nodes Per Ply: n	4
Number of Cycles, Passes	1

Upper Boundary Conditions Lower Boundary Conditions

	Time (m)	Temperature	Boundary
(1) Initial	0	25	50.00
(6) Ramp	1.00	95.00	50.00
(9) Step	60	95.00	50.00
(10) Step	200	95.00	20.00
(14) Step	202	25	20.00
(16) Step	450	25	20.00
(-17)			
(-18)			
(-19)			
(-20)			
(-21)			
(-22)			

Temperature: 0.00 500 1.00E+3 Slices: 1 20 40 50

Microstructure Input

Standard View Table View

Processing properties for HB-210

	Value	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Initial Void Fraction: V0 (%)	0.0254	0	1
Initial Width (for ATP Processing): Tw	26	0	100
Initial Void Temperature: Tv	25	25	500
Initial Surface Roughness Parameter: Rc	0.05	0	1
Resin Viscosity: mu	1e3	1e3	1e5
Initial Void Pressure: Vp	0.101	0.101	0
Void Venting: Vvent	0	0	1
Void spacing: vs	0.0001	0.0001	0.01
Permeability: Kx	1.3e-16	1e-16	1e-12
Permeability: Ky	1.3e-16	1e-16	1e-12
Resin Viscosity: uv	1e3	1e1	1e5

Initial Void Fraction: V0 (%) 2.54E-2

Temperature and Consolidation Profiles

Summary

- Developed unit cell process model that predicts temperature and consolidation of thick section UHMWPE laminates under high pressure
- Model based approach and supporting experiments developed aids in optimization of thermal pressure cycle that improves consolidation at lower pressures without damage to the PE filaments
- Implemented thermal characterization of UHMWPE and associated boundary materials to develop a thermal model in support of process optimization
- Integrated models into CDS software for real-time process optimization for thick section UHMWPE applications

This systematic approach provides insight into the physics of high-pressure consolidation and establish optimized processing and geometric conditions that maximize the structural performance of UHMWPE composites

Acknowledgements

- Team Members:
 - Ahmad Abu Obaid
 - Sagar Doshi
 - Jack Gillespie
 - Bazle Haque
 - John Tierney
 - Alex Vanarelli
 - Newan Dewapriya
 - Abdalsalam Fadeel
 - Undergraduate Students
 - June Yae Jang, Tyler Phommachanh, Adam Higazi Hayden Marquardt
- ARL TPOC:
 - Travis Bogetti
 - Mike Yeager
 - Chris Hoppel
 - James Campbell